

Bridging Organizational Strategy and Research Management: Reflections from TÜBİTAK MAM and the SMART4ENV Project

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Abstract

Research Management and Administration (RMA) is an essential pillar in strengthening the competitiveness, sustainability, and international visibility of research-performing organizations. Within the framework of the SMART4ENV project, supported by Horizon Europe, TÜBİTAK Marmara Research Center (MAM) has undertaken significant steps to professionalize research management practices and align institutional strategy with European research and innovation priorities.

TÜBİTAK MAM's Strategy and Project Management Directorate has developed a comprehensive action plan for enhancing research management capacities. The plan includes the refinement of research group leadership roles, the preparation of a five-year R&D and Technology Roadmap (2025–2029), and the improvement of the integrated Research Management System (RMS) to ensure continuous monitoring, evaluation, and strategic alignment. These initiatives aim not only to strengthen internal governance and research support structures but also to expand the institution's international collaboration and excellence in the field of research management.

This presentation will share TÜBİTAK MAM's experiences from both an institutional and career development perspective. It will reflect on how structured research management contributes to organizational strategy, supports the professional development of Research Managers and Administrators (RMAs), and addresses the challenges of internationalization. By presenting the key lessons learned, the presentation will invite discussion and reflection on professional development of RMAs, further professionalization of RMSs, as well as community building within the European RMA ecosystem.

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